

EFFECT OF ZnO AND Ag NANOPARTICLES ON THE GROWTH OF WHEAT (*TRITICUM DURUM*) AND THE INFLUENCE OF Ag DOPING IN ZnO NANOPARTICLES

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ABSTRACT. The use of zinc oxide (ZnO) and silver (Ag) nanoparticles (NPs) holds strong potential in agriculture due to their antimicrobial properties and ability to promote plant growth. Silver doping appears to enhance the activity of ZnO, but concerns about their phytotoxicity may limit their use. In this study, ZnO, Ag, and Ag-doped ZnO (ZnO/Ag) nanoparticles were synthesized and characterized to assess their effects on the germination, leaf growth, and root development of durum wheat (*Triticum durum*). The results show that ZnO-NPs support germination at low concentrations but become toxic at higher doses, affecting root and shoot growth. Silver nanoparticles have higher toxicity and severely inhibit plant development by disrupting cell functions and causing oxidative stress, especially at high concentrations. However, doping ZnO with silver helps to reduce these negative effects. The doped particles combine the benefits of ZnO with silver's antimicrobial action, reducing oxidative stress and limiting Ag-NP toxicity. As a result, ZnO/Ag NPs may offer a safer and more effective solution for agricultural use, provided their use is well-controlled.

Keywords: ZnO-NPs, Ag-NPs, doping, phytotoxicity, durum wheat.

INTRODUCTION

The increasing use of metallic NPs in various fields, especially in agriculture, is of great interest due to their unique physicochemical and biological properties that give them high efficacy [1-3]. ZnO-NPs and Ag-NPs in particular stand out for their antifungal [2,4] and antibacterial [5,6] properties, positioning them as agents of choice for the control of pathogens. Due to their nanometric size and large specific surface area [7], these NPs interact effectively with microbial cells, leading to their inactivation via mechanisms such as disruption of cell membranes and generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) [4].

In addition to their antimicrobial role, ZnO-NPs show significant potential to promote plant development [8]. They are mainly well known for their beneficial effects on plant growth at appropriate concentrations [9], particularly through their contribution to zinc, a micronutrient essential for protein synthesis and the regulation of enzymes in plants [10,11]. These properties allow them to improve agronomic performance by stimulating plant germination and growth.

Although, the effects of Ag-NPs, although appreciated for their antimicrobial properties protecting against various pathogens [12], are sometimes controversial due to their potential toxicity at high concentrations [13-15]. However, studies show that at controlled levels, Ag-NPs can also promote growth and increase plant vigor by activating certain essential enzymes and physiological processes in plants [8, 16,17].

Furthermore, doping ZnO-NPs with Ag represents a promising strategy to merge the strengths of both materials, ZnO's growth-promoting potential and Ag's antimicrobial effects. This approach is based on the hypothesis that their combination can enhance overall nanoparticle performance while reducing phytotoxicity [18-20]. The resulting synergy could contribute to improved plant productivity, making these nanocomposites valuable candidates for sustainable agricultural applications.

Concerns remain about the potential phytotoxicity of NPs on plants. While these nanomaterials may have beneficial effects at low concentrations, higher concentrations may induce oxidative stress, leading to cellular damage and impaired plant growth. These concerns highlight the importance of thorough evaluations to ensure their safe and effective use in agriculture.

In this context, our study investigates the effect of ZnO-NPs and Ag-NPs on key plant development parameters, including germination rate, leaf elongation, and root development in durum wheat grains. Seeds were exposed to different concentrations of each NPs, and the effect of doping ZnO-NPs with Ag was investigated to determine if this combination could modulate the observed effects, providing the benefits of zinc while reducing the phytotoxicity of Ag. This doping strategy aims to exploit the advantages of both materials while minimizing their adverse effects. The results of this study could provide valuable insights into the safe and efficient use of nanoparticles in agriculture, contributing to the sustainable management of agricultural resources.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Synthesis of nanoparticles

Sigma Aldrich provided zinc acetate dehydrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and sodium hydroxide (NaOH). Silver nitrate (AgNO_3) was obtained from Ampère Industrie. All the chemical reagents were of analytical grade and used as received without further purification. Distilled water was used in all stages of the syntheses and trials. The pure ZnO-NPs and Ag-NPs were synthesized by the precipitation method using, respectively, zinc acetate dihydrate $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and silver nitrate (AgNO_3) as the source of zinc and silver. Ag-doped ZnO (5 %) ZnO/Ag NPs were prepared using the co-precipitation method.

First, a zinc acetate solution was prepared and kept under magnetic stirring for 30 minutes. Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution was then added dropwise under constant stirring until a pH of 12 was reached, allowing a white precipitate to form. The mixture is then allowed to settle overnight. The suspension is filtered, and the precipitate is carefully washed several times with an aqueous solution. The solid obtained was then dried at 100 °C for two hours. Once dry, it was ground and then calcined at 400 °C for 3 hours. A similar procedure has been adopted for the synthesis of Ag-NPs using silver nitrate as a precursor. This protocol is also used in the preparation of ZnO/Ag NPs, where the two precursors are mixed in defined proportions to obtain solutions with the desired doping percentages.

Characterizations of NPs

The crystalline structure of the ZnO-NPs, Ag-NPs, and ZnO/Ag NPs prepared was characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), using a Malvern Panalytical Empyrean X-ray diffractometer with a Cu-K α radiation source ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). Measurements were taken in the 2θ range from 0 to 80°. The crystallite size (D) of the samples was estimated using the Scherrer equation as Eqn. 1.

$$D = 0.89 \lambda / B \cos \theta$$

Eqn. 1

Where: D = crystallite size, λ = wavelength of x-ray radiation, β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the samples, and θ is the diffraction angle.

The morphological feature and the elemental ratio of prepared NPs were characterized by scanning electron microscopy – energy dispersive X-ray spectrometry (SEM-EDX; QUANTA 250[®]).

Preparation of Nanoparticle Suspensions

The ZnO-NPs, Ag-NPs, and ZnO/Ag-NPs were suspended in distilled water to prepare solutions of different concentrations: 0.01 mg/mL, 0.05 mg/mL, 0.1 mg/mL and 1 mg/ml. The volumes required for each concentration were calculated to ensure consistent daily watering of the seeds over the 8 day experiment. In order to ensure a homogeneous dispersion of the nanoparticles, the suspensions were subjected to a sonication treatment.

Wheat seed preparation and treatment

Healthy and undamaged seeds of durum wheat (*Triticum durum*) were selected and disinfected in 5% sodium hypochlorite for 10 minutes to eliminate surface contaminants, followed by thorough rinsing with distilled water. To promote uniform germination, seeds were soaked overnight in distilled water. Twenty seeds of similar size were placed in each Petri dish lined with cotton wool. Treatments were applied daily using 8 ml of nanoparticle suspensions at concentrations of 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, and 1 mg/ml, while control dishes received only distilled water. Each treatment was replicated three times. The seeds were incubated under controlled conditions (16/8 h light/dark cycle, 20–25 °C) for eight days. At the end of the experiment, germination rate (germinated seeds/total seeds), as well as root and shoot lengths, were measured for each plant. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA to assess the effects of nanoparticle treatments. No statistically significant differences were observed ($p > 0.05$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Structural analysis

Fig. 1 shows the XRD patterns of ZnO, Ag, and Ag/ZnO NPs. The pattern of the ZnO/Ag nanocomposite is similar to that of ZnO-NPs, suggesting that there is no change in the crystalline structure during the doping process [21]. The diffraction peaks of the two samples are in good agreement with the hexagonal Wurtzite ZnO data [JCPDS. No 01-089-0510]. There are no characteristic peaks of impurity phases regardless of the dopant concentrations, confirming the high purity of the synthesized powders. The average crystalline size of ZnO-NPs and ZnO/Ag NPs is 27 and 25 nm, respectively.

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of ZnO-NPs (a), ZnO-Ag NPs (b) and Ag-NPs (c).

The XRD pattern of the Ag NPs shows diffraction peaks that are in good agreement with the standard data in JCPDS No. 03-065-2871 and are well characteristic of the face-centered cubic crystal structure of silver. The average crystal size of the Ag-NPs is 26 nm.

Morphological and elemental analysis

The SEM images of the ZnO-NPs, Ag-NPs, and ZnO/Ag NPs are shown in Fig. 2. The SEM image of the ZnO-NPs shows irregularly shaped agglomerates. In contrast, the ZnO/Ag shows a relatively spherical morphology with a homogeneous dispersion of the particles. For the Ag-NPs, the image shows a highly agglomerated, skeletal microstructure with significant porosity due to particle aggregation.

Fig. 2. SEM images of ZnO (a), Ag (b), and ZnO/Ag (c) NPs samples

Fig. 3. EDX spectra of ZnO (a), ZnO/Ag (b), and Ag (c) NPs samples.

The chemical composition of the synthesized nanoparticles is confirmed by EDX analysis. EDX spectra (Fig.3) indicate that the nanoparticles are composed of Zn, O (a), and Ag (c), and the presence of Ag in the ZnO/Ag nanoparticles is confirmed (b).

Effect of ZnO-NPs, Ag-NPs, and ZnO-Ag NPs on germination rate (TG)

The germination of the seeds varied according to the type and concentration of the different nanoparticles (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Effect of different NPs on the germination of the seeds

These results suggest that ZnO-NPs at low concentrations can create nanopores on the seed coat, increasing cell permeability and their ability to absorb water and nutrients [23, 24].

Fig. 5. Effect of different concentrations of ZnO-NPs, Ag-NPs, and ZnO/Ag NPs on seed germination rate after 8 days of exposure.

However, the rate of seed germination decreased with increasing ZnO-NP concentrations (0.1 mg/ml and above). At higher amounts, ZnO-NPs can build up on the outside of seeds or get inside the seed coats, which disrupts important cellular and chemical processes needed for germination. One of the key mechanisms involved is the induction of oxidative stress through excessive generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), such as hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) and superoxide radicals (O_2^-) [25,26]. These ROS can cause lipid peroxidation, leading to membrane destabilization and loss of cellular compartmentalization, ultimately impairing water uptake and metabolic activation in the early stages of germination.

Additionally, ZnO-NPs may inhibit the activity of essential hydrolytic enzymes like α -amylase and proteases, which are responsible for mobilizing stored starch and proteins to support embryonic growth. This enzymatic inhibition restricts nutrient availability, slows cell elongation and division, and compromises root and shoot emergence [27]. Furthermore, Zn^{2+} ions released from the nanoparticles may compete with other essential ions such as Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} , disrupting ion homeostasis and enzyme function [28,29]. These biochemical disruptions collectively reduce cell viability and delay seedling growth. Consistent with these observations, Shyla and Natarajan [28] as well as Solanki and Laura [29] reported that high concentrations of ZnO-NPs negatively affect plant development by altering redox balance, impairing enzymatic activity, and reducing nutrient uptake. Thus, the phytotoxicity observed at higher ZnO-NP levels can be attributed to a complex interplay of oxidative damage, metabolic disruption, and ionic imbalance at the cellular level.

Ag-NPs significantly reduce seed germination, even at low concentrations, due to their early inhibitory effect on the germination process. This inhibition is partly explained by their antibacterial properties, which act not only on pathogenic microorganisms but also on the symbiotic microorganisms associated with the seeds. The latter facilitate the degradation of organic substances and thus play a crucial role in germination [30, 31, 32]. Ag-NPs adhere to the cell membranes of seeds, establishing a barrier that prevents the absorption of water and nutrients required during the early stages of germination.

This reduces embryos' access to nutritional stores, affecting their development. By attaching in this manner, they also inhibit the proper functioning of the necessary enzymatic and metabolic processes, thus limiting the seeds' ability to mobilize nutritional resources. Additionally, this barrier can cause oxidative stress by increasing the generation of ROS, which can harm cellular components like cell walls, DNA, and proteins [33,34]. This damage limits cell viability and interferes with critical metabolic activities. Several studies [35] have

confirmed similar findings, indicating the toxicity of Ag-NPs for germination processes and the cellular systems involved in early growth.

Seeds treated with increasing concentrations of ZnO-Ag NPs show a significantly higher germination rate in a dose-dependent manner. This effect is attributed to the synergistic properties of silver doping, which enhances the photocatalytic activity of ZnO [36,37]. This improvement leads to increased nutrient availability, improved water uptake, and activation of enzymes critical for germination [38,39]. This combination also reduces oxidative stress induced by Ag-NPs. The doping of ZnO nanoparticles with Ag regulates the production of ROS, maintaining them at a controlled level sufficient to stimulate physiological processes without causing cellular damage. This enhances seed germination and growth [40,41].

Effect of ZnO-NPs, Ag-NPs, and ZnO/Ag NPs on leaf elongation

Both ZnO-NPs and Ag-NPs showed an inhibitory effect on leaf elongation (Fig. 6), particularly pronounced at high concentrations (1mg/ml). At lower concentrations (0.1mg/ml), moderate effects on growth were also observed, suggesting a dose-dependent relationship affecting the physiological processes of the plants (Fig. 7).

Fig. 6. *Effect of different NPs on leaf elongation*

Fig. 7. *Effect of different concentrations of ZnO-NPs, Ag NPs, and ZnO/Ag NPs on leaf elongation after 8 days of exposure.*

Exposure to ZnO-NPs and Ag-NPs limits leaf development primarily through the induction of oxidative stress, which results in excessive production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) [42]. These ROS damage cellular components such as lipids, proteins, and DNA, ultimately impairing membrane stability and chloroplast function. This disruption negatively affects photosynthesis by damaging photosynthetic pigments and inhibiting electron transport chains in chloroplasts, thereby reducing energy production required for leaf cell expansion and elongation [43-45]. Additionally, NPs interfere with the uptake and translocation of essential nutrients such as Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , and Fe^{2+} , which are vital for chlorophyll synthesis and enzymatic functions [46-48]. The imbalance of ions and nutrient deficiency reduces metabolic activity and pressure-induced cell expansion in leaf tissues.

Although ZnO/Ag nanocomposites exhibit synergistic benefits that reduce some of the phytotoxic effects of Ag-NPs, the accumulation of Ag^+ ions in plant tissues remains a critical limitation. These ions can bind to thiol-containing enzymes, disrupt metabolic pathways, and lead to cellular toxicity, ultimately resulting in reduced leaf elongation and limited plant development [49].

Root elongation

The results show a general trend towards the inhibition of root growth with increasing concentrations of nanoparticles (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. Effect of different NPs on root elongation.

ZnO-NPs gradually reduce root elongation with increasing concentration. The inhibitory effect of Ag-NPs is more pronounced and is manifested by a more significant reduction in root elongation with increasing concentrations (Figure 9). This difference can be attributed to the higher toxicity of Ag-NPs, which generate more significant oxidative stress, leading to more severe damage to root cells.

Fig. 9. Effect of different concentrations of ZnO-NPs, Ag-NPs, and ZnO/Ag NPs on root elongation after 8 days of exposure.

ZnO-NPs and Ag-NPs inhibit root elongation primarily by inducing oxidative stress through the excessive generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), such as superoxide anion (O_2^-), hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), and hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet OH$). These ROS disrupt redox homeostasis and cause oxidative damage to lipids, proteins, and nucleic acids, thereby compromising membrane integrity and inhibiting cell division and elongation in the root apical meristem. In addition, high levels of ROS can down regulate or inhibit the activity of key antioxidant enzymes such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), and peroxidases (POD), further exacerbating cellular damage [50, 51, 52]. This oxidative imbalance alters crucial metabolic and hormonal pathways resulting in reduced root development, impaired nutrient uptake, and destabilization of the root architecture.

ZnO/Ag NPs also inhibit root growth, but to a lesser extent ZnO/Ag NPs also inhibit root growth, but to a lesser extent than Ag-NPs alone. This suggests that Ag doping in the ZnO matrix may slow the release of toxic Ag^+ ions, thereby reducing oxidative burst and improving biocompatibility. Nevertheless, the potential accumulation of Ag^+ at higher concentrations still poses a toxicity risk due to its affinity for thiol groups in proteins, which can inactivate essential enzymes and disrupt cellular function [53]. Further analysis of the expression and activity of oxidative stress-related genes and enzymes would be valuable to better understand these differential responses.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our study revealed the dose-dependent effects of ZnO-NPs, Ag-NPs, and ZnO/Ag NPs on seed germination and plant development. At low concentrations, ZnO-NPs showed a stimulatory effect on germination; however, at higher doses they exhibited phytotoxicity, negatively affecting root and shoot growth. Ag-NPs, while effective, displayed significant phytotoxicity, which limits their direct use in agriculture. However, doping ZnO with silver reduced these toxic effects while maintaining the beneficial properties.

The results suggest that ZnO/Ag NPs, when applied under controlled conditions, could serve as a promising alternative for increasing crop productivity while minimizing environmental impact. However, further investigation is required into the application of these particles in real agricultural systems, particularly with regard to long-term ecological effects and optimal dosage strategies. Future research should focus on field trials, formulation methods, and the mechanisms governing nanoparticle-plant interactions to ensure safe and sustainable integration into agricultural practices.

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